

An Open Source, Parallel, and Distributed Web-Based Probabilistic Risk Assessment Platform to Support Real Time Nuclear Power Plant Risk-Informed Operational Decisions

Milestone Report: Literature Review, Benchmarking, and Profiling of Current PRA Tools

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Configuration Control

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Executive Summary

This technical report summarizes the work completed for the “Literature Review, Benchmarking, and Profiling of Current PRA Tools” milestone.

Acknowledgments

We would like to acknowledge the support received from Dr. Stephan Ted Wood, the SAPHIRE team leader at Idaho National University and Alp Tezbasaran, a member of the PRA team at North Carolina State University.

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

PRA Probabilistic Risk Assessment

Nomenclature and Notations

Section	Symbol	Representation
2.2.3	K/N	K out of N gates

1 Review of Six Months of the Project

According to the Meeting Notes, the official meetings started on January 26th, 2022. A couple of meetings were set to walk through some basics about the front end, back end, and engine in November and December of 2021.

1.1 Contributors

Dr. Diaconeasa leads the project as a PI with the contribution of Dr. Gupta as a co-PI from North Carolina State University (NCSU) and Wood and Boyce as collaborators from Idaho National Laboratory (INL).

Asmaa Farag, Arjun Earthperson, and Egemen M. Aras, who are pursuing Ph.D. in Nuclear Engineering, are graduate student contributors to the project.

1.2 Initial Capabilities

Only Arjun had a programming experience as a graduate student. Asmaa and Egemen have never done professional programming assignments or used the Git repository. The terminology and process were so far away from them.

Arjun was also experienced with Probabilistic Risk Assessment (PRA) Tools like SCRAM [1].

In general, it can be thought that the graduate student team started the process with very little knowledge and experience.

1.3 Current Capabilities

The team completed the initial benchmark study on April 27th, 2022, and submitted this work to IMECE Conference. The paper was accepted with minor revision requirements with a due date August 3rd, 2022. The team is now capable of using XFTA [3], SCRAM [2], and SAPH SOLVE [4]. The detailed information about this study can be found in Section 2, Benchmark Study.

In the meantime, the team read a couple of essential documents to understand the science behind the topic. These are some of the important ones:

- R&D Roadmap to Enhance Industry Legacy Probabilistic Risk Assessment Methods and Tools [2]
- Enhancement of Industry Legacy Probabilistic Risk Assessment Methods and Tools [3]
- XFTA Version 1.0 Manual [4]

- Probabilistic Safety Analysis with XFTA [5]
- SAPHIRE's Current State of Practice to Meet PRA Demands [6]
- SAPHIRE 8 Basics [7]
- Open-PSA Model Exchange Format [8]
- Fault Tree Reduction and Quantification – An Overview of IRRAS algorithms [9]
- Uncertainty of Measurement: A Review of the Results for Calculating Uncertainty Components Through Functional Relationships [10]
- Sampling Algorithms, from Survey Sampling to Monte Carlo Methods: Tutorial and Literature Review [11]
- Benchmarking as Empirical Standard in Software Engineering Research [12]
- Software Benchmarking [13]
- Reliable Benchmarking: Requirements and Solutions [14]

The team also improved the skills required along the project plan like command line usage, C++ and Python basics, Linux environment basics, and Git and Gitlab basics.

The team can generate fault trees in different variations for XFTA and SCRAM. The event tree generator can create synthetical event trees for XFTA and SCRAM as of now. Moreover, two different way of generating fault trees for SAPHISOLVE has been working. One is modifying the fault tree generator that was available for XFTA and SCRAM; the other is that the script generates fault trees specifically for SAPHISOLVE. Both methods can create fault trees; however, a parser issue in SAPHISOLVE does not let the results get. In addition, more issues appeared with SAPHISOLVE other than the parser when the basic events reach the 10000. The INL team led by Wood is working on that. The benchmarking study will be completed once the parser issue is resolved.

1.4 Documentation

The whole documents are stored in a shared drive which is available only for NCSU contributors. There are a couple of directories in the main folder.

- Deliverables

This directory includes the document that can feed the primary outcomes like benchmark reports and profiling.

- Inputs

The directory includes the sources that come from out of NCSU. For example, the generic Pressurized Water Reactor (PWR) model.

- Literature Review

Published articles, reports, manuals, and books are the elements of this directory.

- Meetings

Meeting notes are recorded and kept in this directory. The meeting notes are crucial and feed all the reports and outputs during the project life cycle.

- Outputs

Outputs directory consists of results obtained. For instance, benchmarking resulted in fault trees and configuration files.

- Project Management

This directory includes the required documents in terms of policy and planners to manage the project efficiently and on time.

- Proposal

The proposal of the project is stored in this directory.

- Publications

This directory includes publications like a conference papers, journal articles, and reports.

- SAPHIRE's-Solver(s)

SAPHSOLVE both for Linux and Windows version are stored in this directory.

1.5 Repository

Currently, the GitLab repository of OpenPRA includes 15 projects. Benchexec Models, Event Tree Generator, Fault Tree Generator, and FT Solver are the projects under benchmarking.

1.6 Following Six-Month Program

Before closing 2022, the team is expected to be done benchmarking and profiling of current selected PRA tools. The design and implementation phases are expected to be started in early January. Implementation of new fault tree and event tree generators were created using the JSON and XML libraries in Python for easier further implementation to

include uncertainty quantification, probability distributions, sensitivity, etc. In addition, further development of the existing SCRAM fault tree generator has been on going and SAPHIRE JSON and OpenPRA JSON formats are incorporated. Also, efforts to change the scram fault tree generator from using the “printer” command to print the input to use python libraries has been started and SAPHISOLVE JSON format has been implemented and tested using JSON library in Python.

2 Benchmark Study #1

2.1 Introduction

The current PRA tools have greatly assisted and enabled the growth of the PRA applications to enhance the safety and security of the current NPPs and improve their different training and maintenance programs. Nowadays, many tools and engines are available to quantify the PRA models. The PRA solvers [15] include SAPHIRE [16] software with the SAPHISOLVE engine, CAFTA tool with an FTREX engine [17], RiskSpectrum tool that uses RSAT engine, RISKMAN tool with various engines, such as Aralia and FTREX engines, XFTA engine [5], and SCRAM engine [1]. The Nuclear Regulatory Commission in the United States uses SAPHIRE, and the nuclear industry mainly uses CAFTA and RISKMAN. Having more than one tool is excellent in terms of verification perspective; however, the issue is that the input file formats are not identical for those tools, making model verification challenging to achieve. In addition, until now, no quantification speed benchmarking of these tools has been performed.

Massive development in the designs of nuclear power plants and large models required more significant computational resources and capabilities. The currently used computational tools and engines have become outdated, seeing minimal core changes for nearly the past two decades. Therefore, research needs to address this challenge, and more powerful and faster tools using the latest parallel and distributed technologies need to be developed.

This study performs a benchmark [14] to evaluate tools and algorithms for XFTA version 1.3.1 and SCRAM fault tree solvers using synthetically generated fault trees with various configurations and sizes. Different algorithms to obtain the cut sets and different methods of calculating the probability are also used for the comparison.

We discussed our methodology in Section 2.2 Section 2.2.1 covers how we generated the fault trees in details. Section 2.2.2 introduces XFTA and SCRAM with their capabilities and limitations in quantifying fault trees; XFTA version 1.3.1 is the one used in all the analyses. In addition, we described the algorithms that we used during quantification.

Section 2.2.3 walks through our benchmarking methodology using BenchExec [18], a reliable benchmarking tool, with its capabilities and limitations. The results of quantification and benchmarking measurements can be found in Section 2.3. Finally, the conclusion of this work is in Section 2.4.

2.2 Materials and Methods

This work includes two main steps, (1) fault tree generation and (2) benchmarking. The fault tree generation step covers producing synthetic fault trees by changing the available arguments listed in Table 1 for users. This fault tree generation is possible by using the script given in SCRAM [1]. The benchmarking step includes quantifying the generated fault trees by setting up the evaluation parameters using two different fault tree solvers mentioned in the previous part, XFTA [4] and SCRAM [1]. In addition to quantification, we also measured the wall time, CPU time, and memory usage for every single case.

2.2.1 Fault Tree Generation

To do a benchmark of different fault tree solvers, we need to specify some of the arguments for that fault tree and be able to produce many fault trees for different arguments. Synthetic fault tree generation is the first step of this work. Table 1 shows the fault tree generator's [1] arguments with its notations.

Table 1. Arguments for fault tree generator, including default values

#	Argument	Notation	Default Value	Benchmark
1	name for the fault tree	--ft-name	Autogenerated	x
2	name for the root gate	--root	NCNAME	x
3	seed for PRNG	--seed	123	x
4	number of basic events	-b	100	•
5	average number of gate arguments	-a	3	x
6	weights for [AND, OR, K/N, NOT, XOR] gates	--weights-g	[1,1,0,0,0]	•
7	average percentage of common basic events per gate	--common-b	0.1	•
8	average percentage of common gates per gate	--common-g	0.1	x
9	average number of parents for common basic events	--parents-b	2	x
10	average number of parents for common gates	--parents-g	2	x
11	number of gates (discards parents -b/g and common-b/g)	-g	0	x
12	maximum probability for basic events	--max-prob	0.1	x
13	minimum probability for basic events	--min-prob	0.000001	x
14	number of house events	--num-house	0	x
15	number of ccf groups	--num-ccf	0	x
16	file to write the fault tree	-o	path	x

As seen in Table 1, sixteen arguments are available for a user to specify any generated fault tree. We changed the number of basic events, weights for gates, and the average percentage of common basic events per gate to create various fault trees. Changing the number of basic events enables the creation of different fault trees sizes. The argument weights for gates allow getting fault trees in different configurations in terms of gates, given that it can not generate fault trees with only NOT and XOR gate but it can for the other gates. Finally, the average percentage of common basic events per gate is to get deeper fault trees as we increase the default number. The configuration and different scenarios that we consider during fault tree generation can be seen in Table 2.

Table 2. Changed arguments for fault tree generator

#	Changed Argument	Notation	Default Value	Changed Values
1	number of basic events	-b	100	1, 2, 10, 100, 1000, 10000, 100000, 1000000
2	weights for [AND, OR, K/N, NOT, XOR] gates	--weights-g	[1,1,0,0,0]	[1,0,0,0,0], [0,1,0,0,0], [0,0,1,0,0], [1,1,1,1,1]
3	average percentage of common basic events per gate	--common-b	0.1	0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5, 0.6, 0.7, 0.8, 0.9

2.2.2 Quantification of Fault Trees

XFTA [4] is a fault tree calculation engine that supports the Open-PSA model exchange format, developed by Prof. Antoine B. Rauzy. It reads a model into one or several text files, then does the calculation defined by a text file containing sequences of commands, in other words, a script file. The script file covers the calculation method and what to print out at the end of the quantification process. XFTA starts with loading the model defined by generated fault tree. The model is normalized as a second step, meaning that common cause failure models are expanded, and constants are propagated. Minimal cutsets of the top event are calculated for the given cutoff (minimum probability and maximum order of cutsets) as a third step. The number of probabilistic calculations is performed from the minimal cutsets as a final step. The most resource-consuming step is minimal cutset calculation. Furthermore, XFTA enables the evaluation of top-event probability, the importance factor of basic events, and sensitivity analysis.

This work sets the minimum probability of 1.0×10^{-14} , and the maximum cutset order is used, 2147483647 (default value), as a cutoff. The expected result is evaluating probability and importance factors using minimal cutsets with a mission time of 8760 seconds. These configurations were put in the XFTA script file.

SCRAM [1] is a command-line risk analysis multi-tool. It is open-source and supports the Open-PSA model exchange format as XFTA. SCRAM is capable of event tree analysis and fault tree analysis using the method of obtaining cut sets Upward (MOCUS), binary decision diagram (BDD), and zero-suppresses binary decision diagram (ZBDD)

algorithms. In addition, analysis of common-cause failure models, probability analysis, uncertainty analysis with Monte Carlo simulations, and generating synthetic fault trees are other features of SCRAM.

MOCUS is a top-down algorithm used by many fault tree engines like Risk Spectrum and SAPHIRE, which incorporates approximations to speed up the calculations. BDD is a bottom-up approach consisting of many complex algorithms of the BDD to find a minimal cut set. This method tends to be faster than MOCUS. However, it is expected to be subjected to combinatorial explosion for extensive models with thousands of basic events and gates with many replicated events. One significant advantage of BDD over MOCUS is the fast and exact calculation of probabilities. CAFTA, RiskA, RiskMan, and XFTA version 2.0.3 use the BDD algorithm to solve fault trees [15].

XFTA and SCRAM can solve fault trees using the MOCUS algorithm from an input file that supports the Open-PSA model exchange format. Moreover, both of them can do probability calculations and evaluate importance factors. In terms of approximate probability calculation, both use rare-event approximations that are valid when the probabilities of events are less than 0.1, which is the case in our work. Both of them are free of charge to use.

In terms of differences between XFTA and SCRAM, XFTA version 1.3.1 is only using the MOCUS algorithm; however, SCRAM can use BDD in addition to the MOCUS algorithm. BDD also allows SCRAM to do exact probability calculations.

2.2.3 Benchmarking Methodology

Benchmarking methodology of fault tree solvers has two main pillars. The first pillar is to create synthetic fault trees by changing the selected arguments, and the second pillar quantifies created fault trees and measures the benchmarking parameters.

As we mentioned in Table 1, sixteen parameters are available for us to change before creating a fault tree. Fourteen of them may affect the quantification results. The quantification result includes a minimal cut set, probability calculation, and importance analysis. The expectation for the first pillar is to get the same result from both XFTA and SCRAM. The changed parameters for fault tree generation are the number of basic events, weights for gates, and the average percentage of common basic events per gate. With the given configurations in Table 2, we can create thirteen different fault trees for the number of basic events greater than 100 for each average percentage of common basic events. In addition to that, we created two fault trees, one's gate is just AND, and the other's gate is OR, which includes only two basic events to see the time for reading a file. We also generated a fault tree that includes ten basic events with AND gate; a fault tree includes ten basic events with ten OR gates for the average percentage of common basic

events per gate is 0.1. We did the same thing for the average basic events per gate is 0.5. To sum up, we created one hundred and twenty-three fault trees for this work.

After creating different fault trees to be solved in both XFTA and SCRAM, it is time to define a framework for benchmarking. For this purpose, BenchExec [18], a framework for reliable benchmarking and resource measurement, was used, and it only runs in a Linux operating system. BenchExec enables an arbitrary command execution with precise and reliable measurement, limit resource usage, and isolate against other running processes. Moreover, it lets users configure resource usage and execute large input files. As a result of benchmarking study, BenchExec generates interactive tables and plots. It measures CPU time, wall time, and memory usage of a tool and allows to specify limits of resources. It also allows limiting the CPU cores and memory regions. The container mode allows for restricted file system and network access. Results from multiple runs can be combined into CSV and interactive HTML tables, of which the latter provide scatter and quantile plots.

In our case study, CPU time, wall time, and memory usage are our benchmarking metrics. The memory limit for each run is set to 63 GiB. The time limit for each run is set to 15 min per fault tree.

The computer configuration used is Dell PowerEdge R710 Intel(R) Xeon(R) L5640 @ 2.27 GHz, 12MiB L3 Cache, 128 GiB ECC-DDR3 RAM. Linux Kernel Version 4.15.0-175. Ubuntu 18.04.6 LTS.

2.3 Results and Discussion

The number of basic events, weights for gates, and the average percentage of common basic events are the parameters that may change our benchmark metrics measurements, CPU time, wall time, and memory.

First, a relationship between the number of basic events and benchmark metrics was evaluated in Table 3. In this case, weights for gates were set [1,1,0,0,0], and the average percentage of common basic events was 0.1 to see the correlation between only the number of basic events and risk metrics.

According to Table 3, XFTA is much faster than SCRAM on the order of ten. In terms of memory usage, XFTA is far more efficient than SCRAM. SCRAM can only quantify fault trees with one hundred basic events for all the gates a given time limit.

Table 3. Relationship between number of basic events and benchmark metrics

Relationship Between Number of Basic Events and Benchmark Metrics		
#	XFTA	SCRAM

# of Basic Events	Status	CPU Time [sec]	Wall Time [sec]	Memory Usage [MB]	Status	CPU Time [sec]	Wall Time [sec]	Memory Usage [MB]
1	100 done	0.0118	0.0628	2.09	done	0.155	0.185	6.68
2	1000 done	0.0651	0.116	5.48	time out	901	904	4220
3	10000 segmentation fault	0.974	2.14	37.2	time out	901	901	10100
4	10000 segmentation fault	8.04	9.27	342	time out	901	902	9270

Table 4. Relationship between number of average percentage of common basic events and benchmark metrics

Relationship Between Number of Average Percentage of Common Basic Events and Benchmark Metrics									
#	The average percentage of common basic events	XFTA				SCRAM			
		Status	CPU Time [sec]	Wall Time [sec]	Memory Usage [MB]	Status	CPU Time [sec]	Wall Time [sec]	Memory Usage [MB]
1	0.1	done	0.0118	0.0628	2.09	done	0.155	0.185	56.68
2	0.2	done	0.0119	0.049	2.09	done	0.185	0.208	7.86
3	0.3	done	0.0118	0.0439	2.09	done	0.146	0.164	6.28
4	0.4	done	0.0122	0.0475	2.21	done	0.153	0.168	6.41
5	0.5	done	0.0129	0.0593	2.22	done	0.145	0.16	6.02
6	0.6	done	0.0116	0.0393	2.22	done	0.156	0.176	6.41
7	0.7	done	0.0144	0.0433	2.36	done	0.154	0.174	6.28
8	0.8	done	0.0131	0.0478	2.19	done	0.192	0.209	7.73
9	0.9	done	0.0121	0.0517	2.22	done	0.201	0.216	8.25

Another significant output is that XFTA is not also capable of quantifying the fault tree containing more than ten thousand basic events. However, this is because of neither time nor memory limit; this is because of an error called "segmentation fault."

Table 5. Relationship between weights for gates and benchmark metrics

Relationship Between Weights for Gates and Benchmark Metrics									
#	Number of Basic Events	XFTA				SCRAM			
		Status	CPU Time [sec]	Wall Time [sec]	Memory Usage [MB]	Status	CPU Time [sec]	Wall Time [sec]	Memory Usage [MB]
1	[1,1,0,0,0]	done	0.0118	0.0628	2.09	done	0.155	0.185	6.68
2	[1,0,0,0,0]	done	0.0137	0.0719	2.49	done	0.145	0.164	6.28
3	[0,1,0,0,0]	done	0.0146	0.0473	2.49	unknown	0.145	0.169	6.28

When it comes to analyzing the effect of the average percentage of common basic events on benchmarking metrics, it is obvious that XFTA is a faster and less memory consumer solver, according to Table 4. The other crucial catch is that as the average percentage of common basic events increases, the time necessary to solve the fault tree and required memory increases. This analysis set the number of basic events to one hundred with default weights for gate, [1,1,0,0,0].

Another significant output weights gates as the default option or with using all gates as AND or OR gates do not significantly affect required time and memory when the number of basic events is one hundred and the average percentage of common basic events is 0.1, as seen in Table 5.

We could wrap up all runs in 50 configurations, as seen in Table 6. Figure 1 shows that XFTA runs in every configuration is much faster than SCRAM in terms of CPU time. Wall time also follows the same patterns as CPU time for each case. SCRAM needs more memory for the same configuration in terms of memory usage, as seen in Figure 2.

According to Figure 1, SCRAM can quantify fault trees for only AND and OR gates when the number of basic events exceeds one thousand for the given limitations. In addition, most of the runs resulted in timeout. On the other hand, XFTA follows a path where the average percentage of the common basic events increases, causing CPU time to increase.

Table 6. Results for all run including every combination

Configurat ion	Numb er of Basic Event s	Fault Tree Configuratio n	Status-XFTA	CPU Time [sec]- XFTA	Wall Time [sec] - XFT A	Memo ry Usage [MB]- XFTA	Status_SC RAM	CPU Time [sec]- SCRA M	Wall Time [sec]- SCRA M	Memo ry Usage [MB]- SCRA M
1	2	02-01-and	done	0.006 99	0.04 06	1.7	done	0.146	0.165	5.89
2	2	02-01-or	done	0.006 99	0.04 06	1.7	done	0.145	0.164	5.89
3	10	10-01-and	done	0.005 39	0.04 34	1.7	done	0.138	0.158	5.76
4	10	10-01-or	done	0.005 96	0.03 14	1.82	done	0.137	0.173	5.76
5	10	10-05-and	done	0.006 03	0.06 01	1.83	done	0.138	0.164	5.89
6	10	10-05-or	done	0.006 02	0.03 15	1.7	done	0.138	0.16	5.89
7	100	100-01-and	done	0.013 7	0.07 19	2.49	done	0.145	0.164	6.28
8	100	100-01-or	done	0.014 6	0.04 73	2.49	unknown	0.145	0.169	6.28
9	100	100-01-and- or	done	0.011 8	0.06 28	2.09	done	0.155	0.185	6.68

10	100	100-02-and-or	done	0.0119	0.049	2.09	done	0.185	0.208	7.86
11	100	100-03-and-or	done	0.0118	0.0439	2.09	done	0.146	0.164	6.28
12	100	100-04-and-or	done	0.0122	0.0475	2.21	done	0.153	0.168	6.41
13	100	100-05-and-or	done	0.0129	0.0593	2.22	done	0.145	0.16	6.02
14	100	100-06-and-or	done	0.0116	0.0393	2.22	done	0.156	0.176	6.41
15	100	100-07-and-or	done	0.0144	0.0433	2.36	done	0.154	0.174	6.28
16	100	100-08-and-or	done	0.0131	0.0478	2.19	done	0.192	0.209	7.73
17	100	100-09-and-or	done	0.0121	0.0517	2.22	done	0.201	0.216	8.25
18	1000	1000-01-and	done	1.14	1.16	83.7	done	0.215	0.236	10.7
19	1000	1000-01-or	done	1.17	1.2	83.8	unknown	0.218	0.24	10.9
20	1000	1000-01-and-or	done	0.0651	0.116	5.48	timeout	901	904	4220
21	1000	1000-02-and-or	done	0.0645	0.103	5.49	timeout	900	901	1140
22	1000	1000-03-and-or	done	0.41	0.468	15.2	timeout	901	901	14900
23	1000	1000-04-and-or	done	0.0694	0.0913	5.62	timeout	901	901	7690
24	1000	1000-05-and-or	done	0.0698	0.115	5.63	timeout	901	902	20700
25	1000	1000-06-and-or	done	0.0748	0.107	5.75	timeout	901	901	7380
26	1000	1000-07-and-or	done	0.0803	0.112	6.28	timeout	901	901	18000
27	1000	1000-08-and-or	done	0.084	0.111	6.53	timeout	900	901	3970
28	1000	1000-09-and-or	done	0.0938	0.127	7.06	timeout	901	902	17600
29	10000	10000-01-and	out-of-memory	251	251	63000	done	0.65	0.691	54.9
30	10000	10000-01-or	killed-by-signal	329	333	62100	unknown	0.661	0.679	55.4
31	10000	10000-01-and-or	segmentation-fault	0.974	2.14	37.2	timeout	901	901	10100
32	10000	10000-02-and-or	segmentation-fault	0.805	0.983	38.3	timeout	901	908	8340
33	10000	10000-03-and-or	segmentation-fault	0.825	1.01	39	timeout	901	903	14900
34	10000	10000-04-and-or	segmentation-fault	0.859	1.04	39.6	timeout	901	902	15000
35	10000	10000-05-and-or	segmentation-fault	0.962	1.14	43	timeout	901	903	15000
36	10000	10000-06-and-or	segmentation-fault	0.964	1.13	42.3	timeout	901	902	9870
37	10000	10000-07-and-or	segmentation-fault	1.02	1.2	45.3	timeout	901	903	15000
38	10000	10000-08-and-or	segmentation-fault	1.12	1.3	48.5	timeout	901	902	15400
39	10000	10000-09-and-or	segmentation-fault	1.18	1.36	50.8	timeout	901	902	17200
40	100000	100000-01-and	killed-by-signal	360	363	61800	done	10.1	10.2	490
41	100000	100000-01-or	out-of-memory	337	338	63000	unknown	10.3	10.3	493
42	100000	100000-01-and-or	segmentation-fault	8.04	9.27	342	timeout	901	902	9270

43	10000 0	100000-02- and-or	segmentation- fault	8.37	8.55	349	timeout	901	903	20000
44	10000 0	100000-03- and-or	segmentation- fault	8.8	8.99	361	timeout	901	903	21400
45	10000 0	100000-04- and-or	segmentation- fault	9.31	9.5	377	timeout	901	902	9140
46	10000 0	100000-05- and-or	segmentation- fault	9.99	10.2	392	timeout	901	902	10800
47	10000 0	100000-06- and-or	segmentation- fault	10.8	11	413	timeout	901	902	8570
48	10000 0	100000-07- and-or	segmentation- fault	11.4	11.6	433	timeout	901	902	7530
49	10000 0	100000-08- and-or	segmentation- fault	12.2	12.4	460	timeout	901	902	10800
50	10000 0	100000-09- and-or	segmentation- fault	13.2	13.4	490	timeout	901	902	5420

Figure 1. Measured CPU time and Wall time depend on the given configurations

Figure 2. Measured memory usage for the given configurations

2.4 Conclusion

In this work, we did a benchmark for two different fault tree solvers, XFTA and SCRAM, with defined configuration. As a result, this work measured CPU time, wall time, and memory usage for every run. According to our results, overall, XFTA is faster and needs less memory for the same configuration than SCRAM. On the other hand, XFTA has an issue for the basic events greater than ten thousand in every combination.

More tools will be used for benchmarking with increasing time and memory limits for future work.

3 Benchmark Study #2

The development of the nuclear industry's Probabilistic Risk Assessment (PRA) has significantly contributed to the design, reliability, and safety of nuclear power plants (NPP). Today, PRAs form integration in all nuclear power plant development stages, including design, licensing, operation, maintenance, and decommissioning. Many legacy PRA tools have been used in the nuclear field; however, more powerful tools are needed to cope with the rapid development of the nuclear industry and NPP designs. These tools are now required to analyze new aspects of the plants that were never envisioned before, and more computational resources are needed.

This study uses synthetically generated fault trees of various sizes and specifications to benchmark fault tree solvers; XFTA version 1.3.1 and SCRAM version 0.16.2. The analysis is performed in two steps. The first step is to compare the probabilities, minimal cut sets, and importance factors. The second step is measuring CPU time, wall time, and the memory usage of each engine for benchmarking. The result for the first step for the same configuration is the same for each calculation engine. Overall, XFTA can complete most of the given runs in a shorter time with less memory usage than SCRAM. All computations and measurements are done on a specified computer.

3.1 Introduction

The current PRA tools have greatly assisted and enabled the growth of the PRA applications to enhance the safety and security of the current NPP and improve their different training, inspection, and maintenance programs. Nowadays, many tools and engines are available to quantify the PRA models. The PRA solvers [15] include SAPHIRE [16] software with the SAPH SOLVE engine, CAFTA tool with an FTREX [17] engine, RiskSpectrum tool that uses RSAT engine, RISKMAN tool with various engines, such as Aralia and FTREX engines, XFTA engine [4], and SCRAM engine [19]. The Nuclear Regulatory Commission in the United States uses SAPHIRE, and the nuclear industry mainly uses CAFTA and RISKMAN. Having more than one tool is excellent in terms of verification perspective; however, the issue is that the input file formats are not identical for those tools, making model verification challenging. In addition, until now, no speed quantification benchmarking of these tools has been performed.

Massive development in the designs of nuclear power plants and large models requires more significant computational resources and capabilities. Currently, 439 NPP are in operation, and 54 NPP are under construction worldwide [20]. Moreover, the U.S. Department of Energy (DOE) is supporting a variety of U.S. advanced reactor designs like Sodium Reactor, Xe-100, KP-FHR, eVinci, BWXT Advanced Nuclear Reactor, SMR-160, Molten Chloride Fast Reactor, Advanced-Sodium-Cooled Reactor, Fast Modular

Reactor, and Horizontal Compact High-Temperature Gas Reactor [21]. Currently used computational tools and engines have become outdated, seeing minimal core changes for nearly the past two decades. Therefore, research needs to address this challenge, and more powerful and faster tools using the latest parallel and distributed technologies need to be developed.

Table 7. Arguments for Fault Tree generator, Including Default Values

#	Argument	Notation	Default Value	Benchmark
1	name for the fault tree	--ft-name	Autogenerated	x
2	name for the root gate	--root	root	x
3	seed for PRNG	--seed	123	x
4	number of basic events	-b	100	•
5	average number of gate arguments	-a	3	x
6	weights for [AND, OR, K/N, NOT, XOR] gates	--weights-g	[1,1,0,0,0]	•
7	average percentage of common basic events per gate	--common-b	0.1	•
8	average percentage of common gates per gate	--common-g	0.1	x
9	average number of parents for common basic events	--parents-b	2	x
10	average number of parents for common gates	--parents-g	2	x
11	number of gates (discards parents -b/g and common-b/g)	-g	0	x
12	maximum probability for basic events	--max-prob	0.1	x
13	minimum probability for basic events	--min-prob	0.01	x
14	number of house events	--num-house	0	x
15	number of CCF groups	--num-ccf	0	x
16	file to write the fault tree	-o	path	x

In this study, we perform a benchmark [14] to evaluate tools and algorithms for XFTA version 1.3.1 (will be called XFTA in this paper) and SCRAM version 0.16.2 (will be called SCRAM in this paper) fault tree solvers using synthetically generated fault trees with various configurations and sizes. Different algorithms to obtain the minimal cut sets and different methods of calculating the top gate probability are also used for the comparison.

We discuss our methodology in Section 2. Section 2.1 covers how we generated the fault trees in detail. Section 2.2 introduces XFTA and SCRAM, their capabilities, and limitations in quantifying fault trees. In addition, we describe the algorithms that we used during quantification. Section 2.3 walks through our benchmarking methodology using BenchExec [18], a reliable benchmarking tool with capabilities and limitations. The results of quantification and benchmarking measurements can be found in Section 3. Finally, the conclusion of this work is in Section 4.

3.2 Materials and Methods

This work includes two main steps, (1) fault tree generation and (2) benchmarking. The fault tree generation step covers producing synthetic fault trees by changing the available arguments in Table 7 for users. This fault tree generation is possible using the script in SCRAM [19]. The benchmarking step includes quantifying the generated fault trees by setting up the evaluation parameters using two different fault tree solvers mentioned in the previous part, XFTA [4] and SCRAM [19]. In addition to quantification, we also measured the wall time, CPU time, and memory usage for every case. CPU time measures the time a CPU was used for quantifying fault trees. On the other hand, the wall time is the actual time taken from the start of running the solvers to the end. Memory usage tracks the amount of memory used for each quantification with the given limit

3.2.1 Fault Tree Generation

To benchmark different fault tree solvers, we need to specify some of the arguments for that fault tree and produce many fault trees for different arguments. Synthetic fault tree generation is the first step of this work. Table 7 shows the fault tree generator's [19] arguments with its notations.

As seen in Table 7, sixteen arguments are available for a user to specify any generated fault tree. We change the number of basic events, gate weights, and the average percentage of common basic events per gate to create various fault trees. Changing the number of basic events enables the creation of different fault tree sizes. The gate weight argument allows generating fault trees for all gate types except NOT and XOR in different gate configurations. Finally, increasing the average percentage of common basic events per gate produces deeper, nested fault trees. The configuration and different scenarios we consider during fault tree generation can be seen in Table 8.

Table 8. Changed Arguments for Fault Tree Generator

#	Changed Argument	Notation	Default Value	Changed Values
1	number of basic events	-b	100	1, 2, 10, 100, 1000, 10000, 100000, 1000000
2	weights for [AND, OR, K/N, NOT, XOR] gates	--weights-g	[1,1,0,0,0]	[1,0,0,0,0], [0,1,0,0,0], [0,0,1,0,0], [1,1,1,1,1]
3	average percentage of common basic events per gate	--common-b	0.1	0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5, 0.6, 0.7, 0.8, 0.9

3.2.2 Quantification of Fault Trees

XFTA [4] is a fault tree calculation engine that supports the Open PSA model exchange format (MEF). It reads a model into one or several text files, then does the calculation defined by a text file containing sequences of commands, in other words, a script file.

The script file covers the calculation method and what to print out at the end of the quantification process. XFTA starts with loading the model defined by generated fault tree. The model is normalized as a second step, meaning that common cause failure models are expanded, and constants are propagated.

The most resource-consuming step is a minimal cut set calculation. Minimal cut sets of the top event are calculated for the given cutoff (minimum probability and maximum order of cut sets) as a third step. As a final step, the number of probabilistic calculations is performed from the minimal cut sets. Furthermore, XFTA enables the evaluation of top gate probability, the importance factor of basic events, and performing sensitivity analysis.

This work sets the minimum probability of 1.0×10^{-14} , and the maximum minimal cut set order is used, 2147483647 (default value), as a cutoff. The expected result is evaluating probability and importance factors using minimal cut sets. These configurations are inserted into the XFTA script file.

SCRAM [19] is a command-line risk analysis multi-tool. It is open-source and supports the Open-PSA model exchange format as XFTA. SCRAM is capable of event tree analysis and fault tree analysis using the method of obtaining cut sets upward (MOCUS), binary decision diagram (BDD), and zero-suppressed binary decision diagram (ZBDD) algorithms. In addition, analysis of common-cause failure models, probability analysis, uncertainty analysis with Monte Carlo simulations, and generating synthetic fault trees are other features of SCRAM.

MOCUS is a top-down algorithm used by RiskSpectrum and SAPHIRE, which incorporates approximations to speed up the calculations. The BDD approach enables the minimal cut set generation and direct calculation of exact probabilities through the quantification of Boolean expressions as reduced order binary decision diagrams (ROBDDs) [22], [23]. This is the preferred method when high accuracy is desirable. However, it is expected to be subject to combinatorial explosion for models with thousands of basic events and gates with many replicated events, as is the case with common cause failure modes. CAFTA, RISKMAN, and XFTA version 2.0.3 optionally use the BDD algorithm to solve fault trees [15].

Fault Trees can be quantified in XFTA and SCRAM using the MOCUS algorithm from an input file that supports the Open-PSA model exchange format. Moreover, both can be used to perform probability calculations and evaluate importance factors, in addition to employing the rare event approximation when event probabilities are small in magnitude (e.g., smaller than 0.1), which is the case in our work. XFTA is free to use, whereas SCRAM is open source.

Regarding the differences between XFTA and SCRAM, XFTA version 1.3.1 only uses the MOCUS algorithm; however, SCRAM can use BDD in addition to the MOCUS algorithm. The BDD algorithm enables SCRAM to perform exact probability calculations.

In this study, XFTA has one run for each fault tree with a MOCUS algorithm. SCRAM has three runs for each fault tree: BDD algorithm run, MOCUS algorithm run with a minimum cut upper bound (MCUB), and rare event approximations in probability calculations.

3.2.3 Benchmarking Methodology

Benchmarking methodology of fault tree solvers has two main pillars. The first pillar is to create synthetic fault trees by changing the selected arguments, and the second pillar quantifies created fault trees and measures the benchmarking parameters.

As mentioned in Table 7, sixteen modifiable parameters are available for us to change before creating a fault tree, of which fourteen affect the quantification results. The quantification result includes a minimal cut set, probability calculation, and importance analysis. We expect identical results from XFTA and SCRAM in the first pillar. The modifiable parameters for fault tree generation include the number of basic events, gate weights, and the average percentage of common basic events per gate. With the given configurations in Table 8, we can create eleven different fault trees for each number of basic events greater than ten. In addition, we create two fault trees, one's gate is just AND, and the other's gate is just OR, which includes only two basic events to see the time for reading a file. We also generate a fault tree that includes ten basic events with AND gate; a fault tree includes ten basic events with ten OR gates for the average percentage of common basic events per gate is 0.1. We follow the same way for the average basic events per gate is 0.5. To sum up, we created fifty fault trees for this work.

After creating different fault trees to be solved in both XFTA and SCRAM, it is time to define a framework for benchmarking. For this purpose, BenchExec [18], a framework for reliable benchmarking and resource measurement, was used, and it only runs in a Linux operating system. BenchExec enables an arbitrary command execution with precise and reliable measurement, limits resource usage, and isolates against other running processes. Moreover, it lets users configure resource usage and execute large input files. As a result of benchmarking study, BenchExec generates interactive tables and plots. It measures CPU time, wall time, and memory usage of a tool and allows to specify limits of resources. It also allows limiting the CPU cores and memory regions. The container mode allows for restricted file system and network access. Results from multiple runs can be combined into CSV and interactive HTML tables, of which the latter provide scatter and quantile plots.

In our case study, CPU time, wall time, and memory usage are our benchmarking metrics. The memory limit for each run is set to 63 GB. The time limit for each run is set to 15 min per fault tree. The computer configuration used is Dell PowerEdge R710 Intel(R) Xeon(R) L5640 @ 2.27 GHz, 12MiB L3 Cache, 128 GB ECC-DDR3 RAM. Linux Kernel Version 4.15.0-175. Ubuntu 18.04.6 LTS.

3.3 Results and Discussion

The number of basic events, weights for gates, and the average percentage of common basic events are the parameters that may change our benchmark metrics measurements: CPU time, wall time, and memory.

At first glance, XFTA can quantify up to 1000 basic events with the average percentage of common basic events per gate of 0.9. However, SCRAM can quantify up to 1000 basic events with all the gates being either an AND or an OR gate. We only consider the fault trees quantified by all engines to compare the results.

Table 9. Probability Results for Quantified Fault Trees

#	Fault Tree Configuration	XFTA	SCRAM-BDD	SCRAM-MCUB	SCRAM-RARE EVENT
1	02-01-and	8.33E-04	8.33E-04	8.33E-04	8.33E-04
2	02-01-or	6.45E-02	6.37E-02	6.37E-02	6.45E-02
3	10-01-and	1.00E-14	1.00E-14	9.99E-15	1.00E-14
4	10-01-or	4.72E-01	3.86E-01	3.86E-01	4.72E-01
5	10-05-and	1.00E-14	1.00E-14	9.99E-15	1.00E-14
6	10-05-or	4.72E-01	3.86E-01	3.86E-01	4.72E-01
7	100-01-and	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00
8	100-01-or	1.00E+00	9.96E-01	9.96E-01	1.00E+00
9	100-01-and-or	1.30E-02	1.15E-02	1.29E-02	1.30E-02
10	100-02-and-or	4.42E-13	4.18E-13	4.47E-13	4.48E-13
11	100-03-and-or	8.47E-09	7.83E-09	8.47E-09	8.47E-09
12	100-04-and-or	2.68E-07	2.34E-07	2.68E-07	2.68E-07
13	100-05-and-or	1.60E-06	1.19E-06	1.60E-06	1.60E-06
14	100-06-and-or	9.17E-10	8.78E-10	9.17E-10	9.17E-10
15	100-07-and-or	4.61E-04	4.18E-04	4.61E-04	4.61E-04
16	100-08-and-or	6.22E-13	5.26E-13	6.60E-13	6.60E-13
17	100-09-and-or	9.37E-03	8.00E-03	9.33E-03	9.37E-03
18	1000-01-and	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00
19	1000-01-or	1.00E+00	1.00E+00	1.00E+00	1.00E+00

First, the probability comparison results are given in Table 9. With the given configuration, although no statistical comparison is made for the results, they are very close to the exact results evaluated by SCRAM with the BDD algorithm. One valuable output is that XFTA's probability results match SCRAM rare event approximation results.

Figure 3. The Measured CPU Time for the Quantified Fault Trees

Figure 4. The Measured Wall Time for the Quantified Fault Trees

Table 10 shows the CPU time results for quantified fault trees for both engines. According to Figure 3, XFTA is faster than SCRAM, on the order of ten, although there is a peak for 1000 basic events for XFTA. Table 11 and Figure 4 show that wall time follows the same pattern as CPU time. Currently, XFTA is two times faster than SCRAM rare event approximation. Table 12 and Figure 5 show the memory usage for quantified fault trees.

In terms of memory usage, XFTA is about three times more efficient than SCRAM rare event approximation.

Figure 5. Memory Usage for the Quantified Fault Trees

Even when the timeout constraints are relaxed, SCRAM can only quantify fault trees with up to one thousand basic events. Another significant output is that XFTA cannot quantify fault trees containing more than ten thousand basic events. Due to the closed nature of the source code, further profiling and debugging could not be performed at this stage.

The other crucial insight is that as the average percentage of common basic events increases, the time necessary to solve the fault tree and required memory increases. This analysis set the number of basic events to one hundred with default weights for gates, [1,1,0,0,0].

Either the default option or other options set for the weights of gates do not significantly affect the required time and memory in the case of the number of basic events is one hundred and the average percentage of common basic events is 0.1.

SCRAM can quantify fault trees for only AND and OR gates when the number of basic events exceeds one thousand for the given limitations. In addition, most of the runs resulted in timeout. On the other hand, XFTA follows a path where the average percentage of the common basic events increases, causing CPU time to increase.

Table 10. CPU Time [sec] Comparison for Quantified Fault Trees

#	Fault Tree Configuration	XFTA	SCRAM-BDD	SCRAM-MCUB	SCRAM-RARE EVENT
1	02-01-and	0.0055	0.0826	0.0821	0.0824
2	02-01-or	0.0060	0.0832	0.0837	0.0917
3	10-01-and	0.0057	0.0847	0.0828	0.0821

4	10-01-or	0.0057	0.0830	0.0818	0.0819
5	10-05-and	0.0061	0.0843	0.0827	0.0825
6	10-05-or	0.0060	0.0843	0.0842	0.0831
7	100-01-and	0.0133	0.0886	0.0873	0.0866
8	100-01-or	0.0151	0.0899	0.0883	0.0875
9	100-01-and-or	0.0120	0.0948	0.0925	0.0934
10	100-02-and-or	0.0126	0.1110	0.1100	0.1110
11	100-03-and-or	0.0118	0.0883	0.0899	0.0879
12	100-04-and-or	0.0119	0.0926	0.0916	0.0934
13	100-05-and-or	0.0128	0.0887	0.0897	0.0870
14	100-06-and-or	0.0120	0.0943	0.0943	0.0931
15	100-07-and-or	0.0141	0.0925	0.0922	0.0915
16	100-08-and-or	0.0130	0.1110	0.1130	0.1130
17	100-09-and-or	0.0123	0.1160	0.1170	0.1170
18	1000-01-and	1.1500	0.1310	0.1300	0.1310
19	1000-01-or	1.1700	0.1340	0.1320	0.1320

Table 11. Wall Time [sec] Comparison for Quantified Fault Trees

#	Fault Tree Configuration	XFTA	SCRAM-BDD	SCRAM-MCUB	SCRAM-RARE EVENT
1	02-01-and	0.0510	0.0885	0.0888	0.0874
2	02-01-or	0.0555	0.0877	0.0882	0.0869
3	10-01-and	0.0591	0.0904	0.0877	0.0866
4	10-01-or	0.0348	0.0887	0.0879	0.0868
5	10-05-and	0.0509	0.0892	0.0883	0.0876
6	10-05-or	0.0393	0.0887	0.0884	0.0874
7	100-01-and	0.0601	0.0936	0.0933	0.0925
8	100-01-or	0.0591	0.0959	0.0931	0.0919
9	100-01-and-or	0.0470	0.0989	0.0981	0.0976
10	100-02-and-or	0.0431	0.1140	0.1140	0.1140
11	100-03-and-or	0.0590	0.0939	0.0933	0.0922
12	100-04-and-or	0.0674	0.0987	0.0973	0.0969
13	100-05-and-or	0.0556	0.0947	0.0932	0.0921
14	100-06-and-or	0.0381	0.0996	0.0990	0.0982
15	100-07-and-or	0.0469	0.0983	0.0981	0.0967
16	100-08-and-or	0.0406	0.1170	0.1180	0.1180
17	100-09-and-or	0.0745	0.1210	0.1230	0.1220
18	1000-01-and	1.2000	0.1360	0.1360	0.1350
19	1000-01-or	1.2100	0.1390	0.1380	0.1370

Table 12. Memory Usage [MB] for Quantified Fault Trees

#	Fault Tree Configuration	XFTA	SCRAM-BDD	SCRAM-MCUB	SCRAM-RARE EVENT
1	02-01-and	1.70	5.89	5.79	5.76
2	02-01-or	1.70	5.76	5.76	5.76
3	10-01-and	1.70	5.63	5.76	5.76
4	10-01-or	1.82	5.79	5.89	5.88
5	10-05-and	1.83	5.76	5.75	5.75
6	10-05-or	1.70	5.76	5.89	5.76
7	100-01-and	2.49	6.28	6.41	6.15
8	100-01-or	2.49	6.28	6.41	6.41
9	100-01-and-or	2.22	6.68	6.54	6.55
10	100-02-and-or	2.09	7.73	7.73	7.99
11	100-03-and-or	2.09	6.31	6.15	6.15
12	100-04-and-or	2.22	6.41	6.28	6.42
13	100-05-and-or	2.22	6.02	6.02	6.02
14	100-06-and-or	2.09	6.54	6.55	6.41
15	100-07-and-or	2.36	6.54	6.28	6.28
16	100-08-and-or	2.22	7.73	7.73	7.86
17	100-09-and-or	2.09	8.25	8.37	8.25
18	1000-01-and	83.70	10.90	10.70	10.70
19	1000-01-or	83.80	11.00	10.70	10.70

3.4 Conclusion

In this work, we do a benchmark for two different fault tree solvers, XFTA and SCRAM, with defined configuration. As a result, this work measures CPU time, wall time, and memory usage for every run. Our results show that XFTA is faster and needs less memory for the same configuration than SCRAM. On the other hand, XFTA has an issue for the basic events greater than ten thousand in every combination.

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